

"THE EFFECTS OF TASK-BASED INSTRUCTION ON DEVELOPMENT OF
COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN ONLINE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN"

Khakimova Nargiz Khayrilloyevna

The Teacher of History and Philology Department
Asia International University.
Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

Email: xnargiz92@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10524832>

Abstract. This article discusses the effects of Task-Based Instruction on the Development of Communication skills of English language learners in the online environment in Uzbekistan. It explores the works of different scientists on Task-Based Instruction and examines the strategies and research in teaching online. The author suggests using a mixed-method design to implement Task-Based Instruction online. In addition, the article recognizes some challenges of implementing this research in Uzbek schools and proposes solutions for overcoming them. Altogether, it presents the positive sides of teaching English online in Uzbekistan if Task-Based Instruction is implemented.

Keywords: Task-Based Instruction, Communication skills, online environment, Task-Based Language Teaching, methods and strategies.

«ВЛИЯНИЕ ЦЕЛЕВОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА РАЗВИТИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ
НАВЫКОВ В СРЕДЕ ОНЛАЙН-ОБУЧЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ»

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается влияние целенаправленного обучения на развитие коммуникативных навыков изучающих английский язык в онлайн-среде в Узбекистане. В нем исследуются работы различных ученых по целевому обучению, а также рассматриваются стратегии и исследования в области онлайн-обучения. Автор предлагает использовать смешанный метод для реализации онлайн-инструкции, основанной на задачах. Кроме того, в статье признаются некоторые проблемы внедрения данного исследования в узбекских школах и предлагаются пути их преодоления. В целом, в нем представлены положительные стороны онлайн-обучения английскому языку в Узбекистане при условии внедрения целенаправленного обучения.

Ключевые слова: целенаправленное обучение, коммуникативные навыки, онлайн-среда, целенаправленное обучение языку, методы и стратегии.

Introduction

Task-Based Instruction (TBI) or Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is a subcategory of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and it differs from traditional teaching methods in the way of using the foreign language inside and outside of the classroom by concentrating on a certain task in the target language. Instead of memorizing grammar and copying the tasks, TBI is aimed at teaching the language by constantly involving the target language in real-life situations through communication and experience. Simply, the language is not frozen but spoken in different backgrounds. This approach is very effective in the classroom environment. However, it would be great to see the implementation of Task-Based Instruction (TBI) in a distance learning environment

for improving communication. Because Uzbekistan has just recently started the adaptation process to online education, this research would have many positive effects in developing the communication skills of language learners.

Due to Covid 19, distance education has become a priority in most parts of the world, including Uzbekistan. Uzbek schools had to practice distance learning which was unexpected and new for Uzbek people. Here my purpose is to understand how physical and virtual classrooms can work together to create better communication and collaboration in the language learning background. If it is possible to teach online language learners with the help of Task-Based Instruction, then certainly there is a chance to innovate in the Education sphere. This work helps to understand how Task-Based Instruction (TBI) can be implemented in a virtual classroom. It opens up the effective ways of developing communication for online learners through Task-Based Instruction (TBI). Also, it assists to predict positive consequences and avoid possible challenges in the Uzbek curriculum.

There are several pieces of research conducted to understand how TBI or TBLT works in the online environment and how it can assist in the development of communication skills. Some studies investigated positive results of TBI on improving Speaking abilities (Albino, 2017; Maming et al., 2022; Nget et al., 2020), and some studies explored the way how communication may be improved virtually (Alshumaimeri & Alhumud, 2021). Speaking abilities of the learners can be upgraded with the help of multimedia and technology (Belda-Medina, 2021; Madhubala & Gheitanian, 2017; Mulyadi et al., 2021; Widiastuti et al., 2022) and in a different environment (Belda-Medina, 2021; Muntrikaeo & Poonpon, 2022). Despite the positive results of these studies, more research is needed in this area to understand what effects Task-Based Instruction (TBI) can have on the communication abilities of Uzbek learners and what if it is applied in an online environment.

This topic lacks real-life case studies on the implementation of Task-Based Language teaching for developing communication skills remotely in Uzbekistan. As a result, we do not have the long-term results that can help us to find out the possible challenges that may appear during the teaching process and long after that and try to prevent them. The only problem that can occur during this project may be the lack of experience with online learning.

The Research questions are:

1. How to develop English Speaking abilities in online learning environment by applying TBI?
2. What are the students' opinions about Task-Based Language Teaching in Online learning?
3. What are the effective ways of implementing TBI in the virtual classroom in Uzbekistan?

Literature Review

The effects of Task-Based Instruction (TBI) or Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) on the development of communication abilities of language learners have been extensively investigated in a variety of studies. Almost all the research had positive outcomes in improving speaking proficiency (Maming et al., 2022; Nget et al., 2020), fluency (Albino, 2017), and communicative competence (Belda-Medina, 2021) of the EFL learners, except the problems with insufficient internet connection and inoperative technology (Alshumaimeri & Alhumud, 2021). The studies took place in real-time either online or offline mode. Belda-Medina (2021) used Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in a setting of Synchronous Computer-Mediated

Communication (SCMC) while Muntrikaeo & Poonpon (2022) wanted to examine the development of speaking abilities of language learners in a Flipped Learning Environment (TGF). Besides, the CALL-Mediated Task-Based Language Teaching was implemented for the online audience (Widiastuti et al., 2022). By dividing the participants of the research into two groups: control and experimental, researchers could compare the collected data and the level of student satisfaction towards TBI (Mulyadi et al., 2021; Muntrikaeo & Poonpon, 2022; Nget et al., 2020). In their study, Alshumaimeri and Alhumud (2021) proved the effectiveness of virtual classrooms to develop communication. Moreover, Lai (2011) suggested that online ab initio foreign classrooms based on Task-Based Instruction can be effective. All studies that are presented here show that the application of Task-Based Instruction (TBI) is suitable for EFL learners of all ages: from schoolchildren (Muntrikaeo & Poonpon, 2022; Nget et al., 2020) to people of old age (Madhubala & Gheitanchian, 2017).

In their study, Maming et al. (2022) aimed to develop the communication abilities of the learners with the help of a Task-Based learning approach. For this, they suggested implementing two teaching methods for separate periods to compare the results. They have chosen 100 random 7 Graders from High school in Manila, Philippines and they used Direct Teaching Method for the first two months. At the end of the first period, they held a Speaking test called Pre-Test to understand how the learners' speaking abilities improved. The Task-Based approach was implemented after that in the same period. The results collected from Post-Test showed the exceptional speaking proficiency of the participants of the Task-Based learning approach compared to the Pre-Test results from Direct Teaching Method. From this study, it is clear that the Direct Teaching Method is not so practical in improving the speaking abilities of language learners because it is a teacher-centered approach. For better communication, Maming et al. (2022) think that it is appropriate to use interactive activities that require students' constant communication in the classroom. In some parts of Uzbekistan, schools still use the traditional Direct Teaching Method. In the case of Filipino students, the Task-Based learning approach had a positive influence on the speaking abilities of the language learners. In the current research, these results can be important.

The same experimental research method was implemented in the Cambodian background. Nget et al. (2020) tried to learn how TBI affects the ninth-graders speaking abilities and their satisfaction level with this approach by dividing the participants into control and experimental groups. The qualitative and quantitative data were collected through speaking tests and a student satisfaction questionnaire. The authors discovered that Task-Based Instruction affected the learners' self-assurance and motivated them to study English better. The only flaw of this research was insufficient time duration (18 hours). So, further research should use extended teaching and learning hours to get better results. This research is going to be conducted over a long period of a year to get better results and reflections from the participants.

Similarly, Albino (2017) investigated how TBI influenced the speaking fluency of ninth-grade learners in Luanda. The author used the research instruments such as audio-recorded picture descriptions and audio-recorded interviews before and after the implementation of the Task-Based Language Teaching approach in the class. These recordings were utilized as feedback tools to calculate the results of the research. The findings revealed an increase in grammatical accuracy,

the development of interactive language, and the development of a certain level of automaticity in speech output. These findings imply that learners who use the TBLT strategy may improve their speaking fluency. The students' opinions on using TBLT in the classroom were positively received, and it had a significant impact on their self-confidence and speaking fluency. Despite the research's success, there are some limitations. For instance, the instruments used there were only analyzed by the author, not by other researchers who may or may not be native English speakers. In addition, the research method was predictable because students were repeatedly shown the same images, which may lead to the formation of predictions in the learners' minds. Simply put, the results may be predictable. Instead of audio-recorded pictures and interviews, this research emphasizes interactive and collaborative speaking activities which involve constant usage of the target language.

The Task-Based Language Teaching experiment with an ab initio Chinese class (A classroom where the language is taught from the start) proved that it would be great to implement this approach from the beginning of the language learning process. However, the most significant was the fact that this study was implemented by several researchers in the online environment. LAI et al. (2011) conducted the research in one of the high schools in the United States virtually and the participants were taught Chinese. To address the research questions, six data sources were created and the data were collected. The study's findings revealed that learners were satisfied with the TBLT approach and that their attitudes were changed progressively. It was clear that an online ab initio Chinese language learners' reaction to this approach was positive. However, the difficulties encountered during and after the research were those related to developing and implementing an online TBLT syllabus, insufficient internet connection, and difficulties working collaboratively and using the target language for instruction. More research is required to learn how to adapt the task design and implement it in an online environment. Before conducting this research, a unique syllabus based on Task-Based Instruction will be developed. The tasks will be organized in a way that only the target language will be active.

Alshumaimeri and Alhumud (2021) investigated Saudi Arabian undergraduate students' opinions on how well communication skills were improved by using virtual classrooms. Their opinions were mostly positive. The idea is that practicing communication skills in online classes provided a convenient and pleasant environment for students. They felt more motivated, intrigued, and confident. To collect the data the researchers used two types of questions and observations which they compared at the end of the study. However, there are some limitations of this research. According to Alshumaimeri and Alhumud (2021), some drawbacks of online learning shown by the investigation were technical issues and a lack of face-to-face engagement. Further research needs to be done to avoid these consequences. In this study, more online face-to-face activities will be an important part of improving communication between the learners.

Technology-enhanced TBLT/TBI can greatly influence EFL learners' listening and speaking abilities (Mulyadi et al., 2021). The study conducted by a group of Indonesian researchers showed significant improvements in learners' listening comprehension. The participants were undergraduate students in Central Java, Indonesia and they were divided into two groups: experimental and control. For the first group, Mulyadi et al. (2021) applied a Technology-enhanced TBLT while the second, control group received a regular online teaching method. The

instruments used to collect data were TOEFL listening sections, group discussions, online presentations, and role-plays. The findings indicated that listening tests and materials had a significant impact on listening comprehension, whereas speaking performance activities produced results that were less than ideal. The perceptions of students on technology-enhanced TBLT need to be taken into account in further studies. This research is aimed to have an online survey that can assess the learners' perceptions of the method.

Computer-assisted language (CALL)-mediated Task-Based Language Teaching approach can be a great experience to learn how to upgrade the learners' speaking performance, nurture creativity, and build self-reflection (Widiastuti et al., 2022). Widiastuti et al. (2022) believed YouTube to be one of the most well-known social media platforms in ELT. In their study, they investigated the possibilities of social media for literacy and language learning. 38 Indonesian undergraduate students studying English were assigned to do video recordings and upload them on YouTube. They were able to recognize their strengths and weaknesses by watching their YouTube video clips. The findings showed that the student's learning experiences and opinions of video recording activities with online YouTube audiences were positive. However, further research involving more students is required. Unlike this Indonesian research, the participants of this research are 100 schoolchildren. While developing their syllabus, it is supposed to include activities connected to social media.

Another study exploring the influence of Task-Based Instruction on EFL learners was investigated in the Spanish background. Belda-Medina, (2021) believed that task-based language teaching (TBLT) in synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) can help to enhance multimodal interaction and communicative competence in language learners. The participants were randomly assigned to collaborate on creating digital infographics based on various language teaching methods. Through semi-structured online discussions, surveys, and observations, mostly positive results were received. The participants' perceptions revealed a high level of satisfaction while using multimedia communication which allowed the learners to interact. However, there are some gaps to reconsider and improve in the future. The participants expressed frustration with the poor quality of the digital materials, the use of technology as a mere substitute, and the absence of peer connection in their live online classes. This study is going to create an atmosphere of peer-to-peer interaction and collaboration among the learners during lesson time.

There is another combination of an approach called Multimedia Task-Based Teaching and Learning (MMTBLT) that Madhubala and Gheitanchian (2017) thought can have an impact on the speaking abilities of language learners. To conduct the research, the authors used a free software program called the Content Management System. There 57 adult Iranian EFL learners carried out speaking test activities with the help of which the authors could examine the accuracy, fluency, and complexity of their speech. At the end of the study, it was clear that MMTBLT could greatly influence all three dimensions of the speaking skills of the learners. The only drawback of this research was agreed to be the student's ability to use prepositions and come up with error-free phrases. Further studies need to take into consideration this limitation and work on it. Some speaking tasks can help to eliminate these problems. This research is going to include activities with prepositions or phrase cards (They are supposed to be presented online in the class).

Muntriakao and Poonpon (2022) investigated a very interesting topic. They want to learn how to integrate task-based language teaching (TBLT), game-based language learning (GBLL) and flipped learning (FL) for effective results in improving non-English speakers' communicative abilities in Thailand and their reactions to it. As usual two groups of ninth graders had two different approaches: the first experimental group practiced learning in a Flipped learning environment, and the second control group had an ordinary class at school. The results were impressive. The findings showed the development of communication skills of the learners and positive attitudes. This study's limitations included the small number of participants and Covid's improper situation, both of which hindered the researchers' ability to fully complete their work. Unlike the research, the current study is going to be conducted after the Covid period. This, certainly, can have a positive influence on the learners' overall condition.

It's apparent that through all the studies, the topic of Task-Based Instruction (TBI) has been widely investigated. The results of TBI are positive and successful in many cases. This approach is very effective for language learners' speaking, listening, writing skills, and even grammar-constructing abilities. Most important, it can change the learners' perceptions completely, making them more confident, self-aware, and independent in using the language in the future. The research that this paper discusses concentrates on developing communication skills with the help of TBI and the level of the learners' acceptance of this approach in the online environment. It is supposed to be a challenging process. However, by applying the carefully organized research method, it will be possible to implement Task-Based Language Teaching in the online environment in Uzbekistan territory.

Methods

To answer research questions, it would be appropriate to use a mixed-method design. For each question, different data instruments can be applied. The duration of this study can be from 6 to 12 months long and the classes will be conducted online. The syllabus based on Task-Based Instruction will be created before starting the school year. 1. How to develop English Speaking abilities in an online learning environment by applying TBI? To develop the communication abilities of the learners, Task-Based learning activities will be included. The effects of speaking tasks can be examined with the help of speaking tests. 2. What are the students' opinions about Task-Based Language Teaching in Online learning? Here, we can use an online survey platform as it would be impossible to collect the data offline. All the research is supposed to be online to enhance the effect. The online survey platform can be created by the researchers and IT specialists and should include a questionnaire about students' perceptions regarding the Task-Based Language Teaching approach. 3. What are the effective ways of implementing TBI in the virtual classroom in Uzbekistan? To answer the third research question, reflections of the learners and educators can be collected immediately after or long after the research (no more than 1-2 years). This can help to identify the possible limitations in the research for future studies.

Research Questions

1. How to develop English Speaking abilities in online learning environment by applying TBI?
2. What are the students' opinions about Task-Based Language Teaching in Online learning?
3. What are the effective ways of implementing TBI in the virtual classroom in Uzbekistan?

Data Collection

Online education has recently received more attention because of the pandemic situation that happened in the world. Hundreds and hundreds of students had to attend schools and educational institutions online. Due to a lack of experience in online education, educational organizations faced some challenges in holding classes at a distance. This study aims to show a new way of implementing physical methods of teaching in the online environment. For this, 100 students of Grade 9 can be selected from the 42nd specialized state general education school in Bukhara, Uzbekistan. (The number of students combining four classes: 25 students from each class). Data collection tools involved in this study can be Speaking tests, Surveys, and Reflections in the Post-Study stage.

REFERENCES

1. Albino, G. (2017). Improving speaking fluency in a task-based language teaching approach: the case of EFL learners at Puniv-Cazenga. *SAGE Open*, 7(2). 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017691077>
2. Alshumaimeri, Y. A., & Alhumud, A. M. (2021). EFL students' perceptions of the effectiveness of virtual classrooms in enhancing communication skills. *English Language Teaching*, 14(11), 80-96. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v14n11p80>
3. Belda-Medina, J. (2021). Enhancing multimodal interaction and communicative competence through task-based language teaching (TBLT) in synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC). *Education Sciences*, 11(723), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11110723>
4. Ollomurodov Arjunbek Orifjonovich. (2023). Metaphoric Analysis of "The Kite Runner" by Khaled Hosseini. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(10), 573-578. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2175>
5. Ollomurodov Arjunbek Orifjonovich. (2023). LANGUAGE AND SOCIETY IN CINEMATIC DISCOURSE. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(12), 44-50. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue12-09>
6. Ollomurodov, A. (2023). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSLATION OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 608-614.
7. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). The Main Features of Conceptual Metaphors in Modern Linguistics. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 365-371.
8. Ollomurodov, A. (2023). CINEMA DISCOURSE ANALYSIS AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS IN LINGUISTICS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 500-505.
9. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., Tashpulatovna, K. M., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). COGNITIVE AND LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF. *VOLUME*, 3, 30-35.
10. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). XOLID HUSAYNIYNING ASARLARI TARJIMALARIDA KONSEPTUAL METAFORALAR TALQINI VA.
11. Ollomurodov, A. (2023). MULTIDISCIPLINARY AND INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDY OF METAPHOR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 136-139.

12. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). METAFORANING KO'P TARMOQLI VA FANLARARO O'RGANILISHI.
13. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). KINODISKURS LINGVISTIK SISTEMANING BIR QISMI SIFATIDA. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(23), 208-211.
14. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). Cognitive-Discursive Approach to the Analysis Of Film Discourse. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(10), 25-31.
15. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., Tashpulatovna, K. M., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). COGNITIVE AND LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF METAPHORS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(3), 849-854.
16. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023, May). XOLID HUSAYNIYNING ASARLARI TARJIMALARIDA KONSEPTUAL METAFORALAR TALQINI VA TAHLILI. In *Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes* (pp. 147-150).
17. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 594-600.
18. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 594-600.
19. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). MAHALLANING JAMIYAT IJTIMOYIY TARAQQIYOTIDAGI O'RNI. *Научный Фокус*, 1(6), 369-371.
20. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 722-727.
21. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir O'g'li. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MAHALLA SYSTEM'S REFORMATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(10), 25-30. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue10-05>
22. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir o'g'li. (2023). The History of the Creation and Formation of the Neighborhood. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(10), 480-485. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2142>
23. O'gli, S. U. S. (2023). ELUCIDATION OF ISSUES OF THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA GUZARS IN OA SUKHAREVA AND HER STUDIES. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(11), 30-35.
24. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 722-727.

25. Shokir o'gli, S. U. (2023). The Essence of State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 554-559.
26. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 488-493.
27. Sadullayev, U. (2023). O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlarga berilayotgan e'tibor: mahalla boshqaruvida xotin-qizlarning roli. In *Oriental Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 551-556). OOO «SupportScience».
28. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 755-757.
29. Shokir o'gli, U. S. (2023). MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 35(1), 79-80.
30. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 132-135.
31. Karimova, G. (2023). SKIMMING AND SCANNING. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 334-335.
32. Karimova Go'zal Ikhtiyorovna. (2023). MASTERING THE ART OF EFFECTIVE SPEAKING AND READING: STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING SPEAKING AND READING SKILLS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(10), 32–38. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue10-06>
33. Qurbonova N.R., & Karimova Guzal Ikhtiyorovna. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF FANTASY GENRE IN 20TH CENTURY. *Intent Research Scientific Journal*, 2(5), 1–5. Retrieved from <https://intentresearch.org/index.php/irsj/article/view/68>
34. Karimova, G. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF FANTASY GENRE IN 20TH CENTURY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 67–71. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25307>
35. Karimova, G. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF LITERARY CRITICISM IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN 20TH CENTURY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 411–413.
36. Shodiyeva, M. (2023). SOCIOLINGUISTICS AND IDENTIFICATION IN THE CLASSROOM. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 494-498.
37. Adizovna, S. M. (2023). Code-Switching and Multilingualism: Exploring the Dynamics of Language use in Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 549-553.
38. Shodieva, M. (2023). UNDERSTANDING SOCIOLINGUISTIC APPROACH IN THE ENGLISH CLASSROOM. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 64-68.
39. Maftunabonu, S. (2023). THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TRADITIONAL AND MODERN TEACHING METHODS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 829-831.
40. Shodieva, M. (2023). MASTERING ENGLISH IN A MONTH: EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR RAPID PROGRESS. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education* (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 83-87).

41. Fayzullayeva, N. S. qizi . (2023). Theoretical Views on the Use of the Term "Concept" in Cognitive Linguistics. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(5), 27–31. Retrieved from <https://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/1685>
42. Fayzullayeva, N. (2024). "AMERICAN DREAM" IN WALT WITHMAN'S POEMS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 220–224. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27940>
43. Sur'at qizi Fayzullayeva, N., & Kilicheva, M. R. (2022). UOLT UILTMAN NASRIDA "AMERIKA ORZUSI" KONSEPTI. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING*, 1(8), 574-576.
44. Fayzullayeva, N. (2023). THE IMPROVING OF LISTENING SKILL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 272–276. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25086>
45. Fayzullayeva, N. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF THE AMERICAN DREAM AND WALT WHITMAN. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(11), 137-142